

evaporated nearly to dryness. To this 2-3 ml of conc. H_2SO_4 was added, and the solution was evaporated on a hot plate to fumes of sulphur trioxide in order to expel nitric acid. The presence of even a small quantity of NO_3 ions increases the solubility of the lead sulphate. The residual liquid is treated with 50 ml of distilled water and the insoluble lead sulphate alongwith silica is filtered of after digesting the solution. The filtrate so obtained is made upto 100 ml in volumetric flasks. 20 ml of the solution was taken out by a pipette in a beaker. To this solution 50 ml of distilled water was added, and the solution was heated. To the hot solution 5% solution of NaOH was added, dropwise to precipitate iron as $Fe(OH)_3$, aluminium goes into solution as sodium aluminate, Cu and Zn also remain in the solution $Fe(OH)_3$ was filtered off. The filtrate was then acidified with dil HCl. To this solution 2 ml of 10% sodium thiosulphate was added to complex copper ions and 2 ml of 5% sodium fluoride was added to complex aluminium ions, 2-3 drops of xylenol orange was added, then solid hexamine was added with agitation until the colour of the solution becomes red (pH 6). The solution was titrated with 0.01M EDTA until the colour changes from red to yellow. The reading was noted and the percentage of zinc in the samples was calculated.

By Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer :

For the estimation of zinc by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer a standard calibration graph was prepared. The absorbances were noted against known concentration of zinc. The unknown samples of zinc were then run through the instrument and the absorbances were noted. By interpolating the values in the standard graph the percentage of Zn was determined.

The results obtained by this method have been compared successfully with those obtained by instrumental method i.e. the samples were run on Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer and the results are given in the Table :

Percentage of Zn		
	By A.A.S.	Proposed method
1.	1.10	1.05
2.	0.50	0.42
3.	10.00	9.75
4.	3.20	3.10
5.	6.00	5.60
6.	0.30	0.12
7.	00.50	0.37
8.	1.20	0.99
9.	5.20	4.97
10.	4.36	4.06

Results and Discussion

Xylenol orange forms complex with zinc at pH 6 which was maintained by Hexaine (Hexamethylene

tetramine) but the Zn-EDTA complex is more stable than dye-Zn complex and at the equivalence point all the zinc ions are complexed with EDTA and the xylenol orange dye remains in the solution which is yellow in colour. Copper and aluminium do not interfere as they have already been complexed with sodium thiosulphate and sodium fluoride respectively. Magnesium and calcium also do not interfere as they do not form complex at pH 6.

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Photometric Study of Uranyl-Terramycin Complex*

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THE spectrophotometric investigation of uranyl-tetramycin complex in solution has been studied photometrically at pH 1.3. The composition of the complex is established by Job's and Slope ratio methods as 1 : 1. The stability constant calculated from the data obtained in Job's method is 1.9×10^9 . Beer's law is obeyed.

A survey of literature has revealed that much work has not been done on the "Metal complexes of antibiotics" particularly of terramycin. Metal complexes of streptomycin have been studied by Foye and Lange¹ and Zahn and Eisenbrandt². Uranyl-streptomycin complex has been recently studied spectrophotometrically by Agarwal *et al*³. The spectrophotometric investigation of uranyl-tetramycin complex has been carried out and results are communicated here.

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Experimental

All the chemicals employed are of analytical grade. Spectrophotometric measurements were made with Elico Spectrocol model CL-23 (India) and pH measurements with Elico Digital pH Meter model LI-120. The reagent solution was prepared in 1,4-dioxane. All the other solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

Absorbance of the reagent and the reaction mixture consisting of uranyl ion and the reagent is measured in the pH range 1-4.5 in the wavelength range 400 nm to 650 nm. The absorbance difference for the reaction mixture (metal ion+excess reagent) and the reagent was maximum at 425 nm. Hence further studies were carried out at this wavelength.

Effect of pH :

To the buffered solution (pH 1.3 to 4.5) metal solution and the reagent solution were added so that the overall concentration of each component is $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. The absorbance for each reaction mixture is measured against the buffer solution as the blank. The absorbance of the mixture increased while that of the reagent decreased with increase in pH. However, at pH's higher than 2.5 the solution became turbid slowly and hence further studies are restricted to pH 1.3.

Obedience of Beer's law :

The absorbance of the reaction mixture varied linearly with the concentration of uranium in presence of excess of reagent. This shows that small amounts of uranium can be estimated colorimetrically with the reagent.

Composition and Stability constant :

Slope ratio method and Job's method indicated that the composition of the complex is 1 : 1. The stability of the complex is calculated from the data obtained in the Job's method and is 1.9×10^3 .

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Quantitative Separation of Co^{++} or Cd^{++} or Cu^{++} from Ca^{++} and PO_4^{3-} and Their Complexometric Determination

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THE need for a rapid and quantitative separation and estimation of Co^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} ; Cd^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} and Cu^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} was felt during the investigation of these cation exchange reactions in Hydroxyapatite, the prototype of the inorganic constituent of bones and teeth. The present communication has been an attempt to arrive at optimum conditions for such separation and to investigate the suitability of the complexometric titration for their subsequent quantitative determination.

Procedure : To a convenient volume of a weakly acidic (HCl) synthetic solution of Ca^{2+} , Co^{2+}/Cd^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} ions, 5% solution of sodium citrate was added followed by a slight excess of 7%, NH_4CNS solution (for Co^{2+} till the solution was blue), heated just to boiling and to the hot solution 2 ml of pyridine was added. It was shaken well for 5 min and the crystalline precipitates of Co^{2+}/Cd^{2+} was allowed to settle to room temperature, filtered and the precipitate was washed thoroughly with a solution containing 1% pyridine and 1% NH_4CNS . It was then dissolved in minimum volume of 0.6M warm HCl. The solution thus containing Co^{2+}/Cd^{2+} is made up to a known volume, to a convenient aliquot of this solution 0.1 M NaOH was added to just neutral (methyl red indicator for Cd^{2+} and appearance of a slight blue precipitate for Co^{2+}).

In case of Co^{++} the solution after neutralisation was diluted to 100 ml, 5 ml of 5% NaAc was added followed by Murexide indicator. Buffer (NH_4Cl/NH_4OH) pH ~ 10 was added till the solution was yellow. The Co^{2+} was then determined by titrating against 0.01M E. D. T. A. till a sharp colour change from orange to pure pink was obtained.

In case of Cd^{2+} , to the solution after neutralisation 5 ml of buffer pH ~ 10 was added followed by 3 drops of Eriochrome Black T indicator and titrated against 0.01 M E.D.T.A. till a sharp colour change from wine red to pure blue resulted. For the Cu^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} system the Cu^{++} in a convenient volume of the solution was precipitated by the addition of a solution containing 32% pyridine and 22% salicylic acid. The precipitate was filtered washed with a solution containing 5% solution of the precipitating reagent. It was dissolved in 0.6M warm HCl. To a known volume of this solution 0.1 M